

Efficient synthesis of 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene and 6H-benzo[c]chromene derivatives via 6π electrocyclization[†]

Shubhendu Dhara, Tumpa Gorai, Atiur Ahmed and Jayanta K. Ray*

Department of Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur-721 302, Paschim Medinipore, West Bengal, India

E-mail : jkray@chem.iitkgp.ernet.in

Manuscript received 07 June 2013, accepted 10 June 2013

Abstract : An efficient and very simple method has been developed for the synthesis of 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene, 6H-benzo[c]chromene and various types of bicyclic benzenoid derivatives via 6π -electron electrocyclization reaction, followed by deacetylation.

Keywords : 2-Halovinylaldehyde, nano-palladium, Wittig reaction, electrocyclization.

Introduction

Electrocyclization of conjugated polyene is a versatile synthetic methodology for the formation of C-C and C-heteroatom bonds. Various carbocyclic and heterocyclic natural products have been synthesised using electrocyclization as one of the key synthetic steps¹. Presence of 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene and 6H-benzo[c]chromene moiety as the building blocks in many naturally occurring and biologically active compounds (1-4)² (Fig. 1) of therapeutic importance have been illustrated in organic chemistry. These skeletons are useful precursors for the total synthesis of many bioactive natural products and synthetic polymers of industrial importance. As a result, development of efficient routes for the synthesis of dihydrophenanthrene and chromene skeletons have remained an active research area for the past few decades. In literature, various reports are there for the synthesis of these carbo- and oxa-cycles³. Among them, Ram *et al.*⁴ reported methylsilane-mediated synthesis of 9,10-dihydrophenanthrenes. Chien-Hong Cheng *et al.*⁵ reported Pd-catalysed synthesis of dihydrophenanthrene derivatives and polyaromatic derivatives. Dagmar C. Kapeller and Stefan Brase reported solid-phase synthesis of chromene natural products via domino oxa-Michael-Aldol condensation, followed by successive steps of Wittig reaction,

Diels-Alder cycloaddition and cleavage⁶. Ming-Chang P. Yeh *et al.*⁷ synthesised phenanthrene derivatives via gold(I)-catalyzed hydroarylation of cyclohexane-1,3-dienes bearing an aryl group and a *gem*-diester in a 1,4-addition manner and in a diastereoselective fashion to afford perhydrophenanthrene rings. Ullrich Scherf *et al.*⁸ reported Ni-catalysed synthesis of 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene derivatives.

Fig. 1. Some biologically active dihydrophenanthrene and chromene natural products.

In most of the literature reports⁹, they used expensive metal catalysts and yields were not so much satisfactory.

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Scheme 1. Preparation of trienes.

This directed our interest towards the search for an efficient synthetic method for the synthesis of 9,10-dihydrophenanthrene and fused-heterocyclic skeleton. Recently our group reported a novel Pd-catalysed cyclisation method¹⁰ for the construction of various phenanthrene derivatives starting from 2-halovinylaldehyde. Keeping this in mind, we started our journey from this cheap starting material.

In continuation of work on Pd-mediated synthetic methodology¹¹, herein we report an efficient 6π -electrocyclization reaction towards the synthesis of 9,10-dihydrophenanthrenes and 6*H*-benzo[*c*]chromene analogues.

Results and discussion

At first, we have synthesised the precursor (5) for electrocyclization reaction via two steps starting from 2-bromovinylaldehydes (Scheme 1). When 2-bromovinylaldehydes (1) were treated with methyl acrylate in presence of Na_2CO_3 as base and PdCl_2 as catalyst in water as solvent (nano-Pd)¹², it afforded the compound (2) in quantitative yield. Furthermore, when 2 was treated with 1-(tri-phenylphosphanylidene)-propan-2-one ($\text{Ph}_3\text{P}=\text{CH}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}_3$), it underwent Wittig reaction¹³ to give the triene (5) in good yield.

These trienes were then subjected to electrocyclization reaction conditions. Initially we started heating process from 80 °C in different types of polar and non polar solvents in air. At this temperature only 20–30% conversion of the starting material was obtained after 5–7 h. When we heated the triene (3) at about 125–130 °C, it afforded two products 4a and 4b in almost 4 : 1 ratio. Then finally we optimised the reaction conditions (Table

1, entry 3) at 125–130 °C in DMA solvent and in air. In 5–7 h all the starting material was consumed and two aromatised dihydrophenanthrenes (4a) and deacetylated dihydrophenanthrene (4b) were obtained in good yields.

Table 1. Optimisation of the condition for electrocyclization^a

Entry	Solvent	Time (h)	Conversion (%)
1	Bu_2O	10	45–50
2	CH_3CN	12	30
3	DMA	5–7	> 95
4	DMF	Overnight	70
5	Toluene	16	55

^a1 mmol of the substrate was taken in 3–4 ml of solvents.

With the optimised reaction conditions in hand, we then generalised our methodology with different substrates containing varying functionality (Scheme 2, Table 2). We found that this method resulted the dihydrophenanthrene derivatives in good to excellent yields even in presence of the functional groups like : OMe, Me, di-OMe groups and heterocyclic ring in the substrate (like : Ox cycle) and afforded 6*H*-benzo[*c*]chromene in quite good yield. In case of the $-\text{NO}_2$ as substituent (like : 7-nitro- α -tetralone) addition of methyl acrylate unit via nano-Pd Heck type of reaction, was unsuccessful.

Further, we wanted to study the efficiency of this method on monocyclic non-benzenoid aliphatic ketones. We observed that this method also works well in some monocyclic ketones. Cyclization of monocyclic trienes

Scheme 2. Electrocyclization of the trienes.

Table 2. Substrate variability of electrocyclization^a

Entry	Substrate		Yield ^b (%)	
	R ₁	X	A	B
1	H	CH ₂	67% (6aa)	29% (6ba)
2	8-OMe	CH ₂	51% (6ab)	42% (6bb)
3	7-OMe	CH ₂	55% (6ac)	31% (6bc)
4	H	CH-Me	66% (6ad)	21% (6bd)
5	6-OMe	CH ₂	72% (6ae)	16% (6be)
6	6,7-OMe	CH ₂	44% (6af)	24% (6bf)
7	H	O	63% (6ag)	32% (6bg)

^aReagents and conditions : triene **5** (1 mmol), dry DMA (3–4 ml), 125–130 °C.

^bIsolated yields.

(7) also resulted in two bicyclic benzenoid derivatives (**8a**) and (**8b**) almost in same proportions as in the case of **5** (Scheme 3). We tried this method only for 5- to 8-membered ring systems. This is one of the important synthetic methods for the synthesis of bicyclic benzenoid compounds in excellent yield. The trienes (**7**) were synthesised using the same protocol as in the case of benzenoid derivatives (Scheme 1).

Using the aforesaid optimised reaction conditions for the electrocyclization, the trienes of the corresponding monocyclic derivatives were subjected to thermal cyclization, which resulted in two aromatised bicyclic benzenoid products – one with adjacent CO₂Me and COMe (A) and the other deacetylated product (B).

Scheme 3. Cyclization of monocyclic trienes.

Here we tried to find out the efficiency of the electrocyclization process in the case of different ring

Table 3. Substrate scope^a

Entry	Substrate	Product yield ^b (%)	
		A	B
1		75% (8aa)	21% (8ba)
2		81% (8ab)	Trace
3		69% (8ac)	10% (8bc)
4		67% (8ad)	23% (8bd)
5		68% (8ae)	25% (8be)

^aReagents and conditions : triene **7** (1 mmol), dry DMA (3–4 ml), 125–130 °C.

^bIsolated yields.

size of the monocyclic system.

When we tried to find out the mechanistic course of the reaction, we found that during the cyclization process both the products get aromatised under areal oxidation¹⁴ condition. But actual mechanism of the elimination of the -COMe group in the second product is not clear to us. It was supposed that adjacent ester group may have some influence in the deacetylation process¹⁵.

Experimental

¹H NMR (200 MHz) spectra were recorded on a BRUKER-AC 200 MHz spectrometer. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm from tetramethylsilane with the solvent resonance as the internal standard (deuteriochloroform : 7.26 ppm). Data are reported as follows : chemical shifts, multiplicity (s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, m = multiplet), coupling constant (Hz). ¹³C NMR (50 MHz) spectra were recorded on the same spectrometer with complete proton decoupling. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm from tetramethylsilane with the solvent resonance as the internal standard (deuteriochloroform : 77.0 ppm).

EIMS (70 eV) spectra were taken using a VG Autospec M mass spectrometer. Chromatographic (CC) purification was done with either 60–120 or 100–200 mesh silica gel (SRL). For reaction monitoring, precoated silica gel 60 F254 TLC sheets (Merck) were used. Petroleum ether (PE) refers to the fraction boiling in the range 60–80 °C. DMA was dried, distilled and stored over molecular sieves (4 Å).

General procedure for the synthesis of 3-(2-formyl-3,4-dihydronaphthalen-1-yl)acrylic acid derivative : 2-Bromovinylaldehyde (1 mmol), methyl acrylate (1.5 mmol), Na₂CO₃ (4 mmol), PdCl₂ (cat. Amount.), tetrabutylammonium chloride (1 mmol) were taken in 3 ml water in a two-necked round bottom flask and stirred at room temperature for 3–4 h. After completion of the reaction, it was extracted three times with ethyl acetate and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure and the product was purified by silica gel (60–120 mesh) CC using EtOAc : PE as eluent.

3-(2-Formyl-4-methyl-3,4-dihydronaphthalen-1-yl)acrylic acid methyl ester (2; R₁ = H, X = CH(Me)) : ¹H NMR : δ 10.09 (1H, s), 7.85 (1H, d, *J* 15.8 Hz), 7.25–7.39 (4H, m), 6.19 (1H, d, *J* 15.8 Hz), 3.83 (3H, s), 2.95 (1H, q, *J* 6.8 Hz), 2.51–2.64 (2H, m), 1.20 (3H, d, *J* 6.8 Hz); ¹³C NMR : δ 191.2, 165.7, 154.3, 147.3, 143.3, 138.5, 135.5, 131.8, 131.1, 128.6, 127.0, 126.7, 52.1, 31.4, 27.99, 19.5.

General procedure for the synthesis of triene derivative :

1-(Triphenylphosphanylidene)-propan-2-one (1.5 mmol) was taken in 3 ml DCM in a two-necked round bottom flask. A solution of aldehyde in 3 ml DCM was added to it dropwise at 0 °C under nitrogen atmosphere. The resulting mixture was stirred at 25 °C until completion of the reaction (TLC). The solvent was then evaporated under reduced pressure to give the crude product which was purified by CC using PE : EtOAc as the eluent.

3-[4-Methyl-2-(3-oxo-but-1-enyl)-3,4-dihydronaphthalen-1-yl]acrylic acid methyl ester (5; R₁ = H, X = CH(Me)) : ¹H NMR : δ 7.81 (2H, dd, *J* 10.4 Hz), 7.17–

7.34 (4H, m), 6.42 (1H, d, *J* 16.0 Hz), 6.12 (1H, d, *J* 15.8 Hz), 3.84 (3H, s), 2.98 (1H, q, *J* 6.8 Hz), 2.42–2.72 (2H, m), 2.34 (3H, s), 1.24 (3H, d, *J* 7 Hz); ¹³C NMR : δ 198.7, 166.7, 142.2, 141.1, 140.7, 138.3, 133.7(2C), 132.9, 129.4, 128.3, 126.9, 126.7, 126.3, 52.1, 32.5, 31.9, 27.9, 19.7.

General procedure for the electrocyclization :

Compound **5** (1 mmol) was taken in 3 ml of dry DMA in a 25 ml two-necked round bottomed flask fitted with a condenser. Then the mixture was heated to 120–130 °C temperature in air for 5–7 h. After completion of the reaction (TLC), it was concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude product was purified by CC to obtain the desired products.

2-Acetyl-9,10-dihydrophenanthrene-3-carboxylic acid methyl ester (6aa) : Brown liquid; yield : 68%; R_f (silica gel, PE : EtOAc 5 : 1) : 0.6; ¹H NMR : δ 8.24 (1H, s), 7.84 (1H, d, *J* 6.6 Hz), 7.29–7.39 (4H, m), 3.96 (3H, s), 2.95 (4H, s), 2.59 (3H, s); ¹³C NMR : δ 203.0, 167.8, 141.81, 141.5, 137.6, 136.7, 133.0, 128.9, 128.6, 128.0, 127.5, 126.8, 125.2, 124.4, 52.8, 29.2, 28.6, 22.9; HRMS Calcd. for C₁₈H₁₆O₃Na [M + Na] : 303.0997. Found : 303.0936.

9,10-Dihydrophenanthrene-3-carboxylic acid methyl ester (6ba) : Yellow liquid; yield : 29% ; R_f (silica gel, PE : EtOAc 5 : 1) : 0.8; ¹H NMR : δ 8.46 (1H, s), 7.91 (2H, t, *J*₁ 8.2, *J*₂ 8.6 Hz), 7.15–7.55 (4H, m), 3.98 (3H, s), 2.94 (4H, s); ¹³C NMR : δ 167.5, 142.9, 137.4, 135.0, 133.9, 129.2, 128.7, 128.5, 128.4, 128.2, 127.4, 125.2, 124.2, 52.3, 29.5, 28.8; HRMS Calcd. for C₁₆H₁₄O₂Na [M + Na] : 261.0891. Found : 261.0810.

Conclusion

We have developed a very simple and efficient method for the synthesis of dihydrophenanthrenes, indane and tetrahydronaphthalene derivatives in excellent yields from readily available starting materials. Various other heterocyclic (like : oxa-cycles) derivatives can also be easily synthesised by this methodology. This methodology can also be useful for the construction of many hetero- and carbocycle-based natural products with potential pharmacological importances.

Acknowledgement

SD thanks CSIR, New Delhi for the fellowship. DST is also thanked for providing funds for the project and creating 200 MHz NMR facility under the IRPHA programme.

References

- (a) P. Sharma, N. Griffiths and J. E. Moses, *Org. Lett.*, 2008, **10**, 4025; (b) P. Sharma and J. E. Moses, *Synlett.*, 2010, 525; (c) S. J. Eade, M. W. Walter, C. Byrne, B. Odell, R. Rodriguez, J. E. Baldwin, R. M. Adlington and J. E. Moses, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2008, **73**, 4830; (d) Y. Kobayashi, T. Fujimoto and T. Fukuyama, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **121**, 6501; (e) M. Gallant, J. T. Link and S. J. Danishefsky, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1993, **58**, 343; (f) A. F. rstner, M. M. Domostoj and B. Scheiper, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 11620; (g) J. B. Hendrickson and J. G. De Vries, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1982, **47**, 1148; (h) M. Ishikura, A. Hino, T. Yaginuma, I. Agata and N. Katagiri, *Tetrahedron*, 2000, **56**, 193.
- (a) X.-Y. Wang, C.-Q. Ke, C.-P. Tang, D. Yuan and Y. Ye, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 2009, **72**; (b) S. Ross, R. Minard and M. Hamma, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 1985, **48**, 835; (c) C.-L. Lee, F.-R. Chang, M.-H. Yen, D. Yu, Y.-N. Liu, K. F. Bastow, S. L. Morris-Natschke, Y.-C. Wu and K. H. Lee, *J. Nat. Prod.*, 2009, **72**, 210.
- (a) E. Ballerini, L. Minuti, O. Piermatti and F. Pizzo, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2009, **74**, 4311; (b) B.-C. Hong, P. Kotame, C.-W. Tsai and J.-H. Liao, *Org. Lett.*, 2010, **12**, 776; (c) V. J. Ram, P. Srivastava and A. S. Saxena, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2001, **66**, 5333; (d) E. Ballerini, L. Minuti and O. Piermatti, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2010, **75**, 4251; (e) D. C. Kapeller and S. Bräse, *ACS Comb. Sci.*, 2011, **13**, 554; (f) B. R. Kusuma, L. B. Peterson, H. Zhao, G. Vielhauer, J. Holzbeierlein and B. S. J. Blagg, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2011, **54**, 6234; (g) R. Pratap and V. J. Ram, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2007, **48**, 6318; (g) C. S. Cho, D. K. Lim, J. Q. Zhang, T. J. Kim and S. C. Shim, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 5653.
- R. Pratap and V. J. Ram, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2007, **72**, 7402.
- T. T. Jayanth, M. Jeganmohan and C.-H. Cheng, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2004, **69**, 8445.
- D. C. Kapeller and S. Bräse, *ACS Comb. Sci.*, 2011, **13**, 554.
- M.-C. P. Yeh, Y.-S. Chou, T.-C. Lin and L.-Y. Tseng, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2011, **76**, 4027.
- H. A. Reisch, V. Enkelmann and U. Scherf, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1999, **64**, 655.
- For selected papers on the cyclotrimerization of arynes with unsaturated compounds, such as alkynes, allenes, alkenes, or arynes, to construct the phenanthrene frameworks, see : (a) D. Peña, S. Escudero, D. Pérez, E. Guitián and L. Castedo, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 1998, **37**, 2659; (b) D. Peña, D. Pérez, E. Guitián and L. Castedo, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1999, **121**, 5827; (c) D. Peña, D. Pérez, E. Guitián and L. Castedo, *Org. Lett.*, 1999, **1**, 1555; (d) D. Peña, A. Cobas, D. Pérez, E. Guitián and L. Castedo, *Org. Lett.*, 2000, **2**, 1629; (e) D. Peña, D. Pérez, E. Guitián and L. Castedo, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2000, **65**, 6944; (f) J. Caeiro, D. Peña, A. Cobas, D. Pérez and E. Guitián, *Adv. Synth. Catal.*, 2006, **348**, 2466; (g) I. Quintana, A. J. Boersma, D. Peña, D. Pérez and E. Guitián, *Org. Lett.*, 2006, **8**, 3347; (h) C. Romero, D. Peña, D. Pérez and E. Guitián, *Chem. Eur. J.*, 2006, **12**, 5677; (i) K. V. Radhakrishnan, E. Yoshikawa and Y. Yamamoto, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1999, **40**, 7533; (j) E. Yoshikawa and Y. Yamamoto, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2000, **39**, 173; (k) E. Yoshikawa, K. V. Radhakrishnan and Y. Yamamoto, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2000, **122**, 7280; (l) Z. Liu, X. Zhang and R. C. Larock, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **127**, 15716; (m) Z.-J. Liu and R. C. Larock, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2007, **72**, 223; (n) Z.-J. Liu and R. C. Larock, *Angew. Chem., Int. Ed.*, 2007, **46**, 2535; (o) T. T. Jayanth, M. Jeganmohan and C.-H. Cheng, *J. Org. Chem.*, 2004, **69**, 8445; (p) J.-C. Hsieh, D. K. Rayabarapu and C.-H. Cheng, *Chem. Commun.*, 2004, 532; (q) S. Bhuvaneshwari, M. Jeganmohan and C.-H. Cheng, *Org. Lett.*, 2006, **8**, 5581; (r) T.-T. Jayanth and C.-H. Cheng, *Chem. Commun.*, 2006, 894; (s) J. L. Henderson, A. S. Edwards and M. F. Greaney, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **128**, 7426.
- R. Jana, I. Chatterjee, S. Samanta and J. K. Ray, *Org. Lett.*, 2008, **10**, 4795.
- (a) S. K. Mal, D. Ray and J. K. Ray, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2004, **45**, 277; (b) D. Ray, S. K. Mal and J. K. Ray, *Synlett.*, 2005, 2135; (c) D. Ray and J. K. Ray, *Org. Lett.*, 2007, **9**, 191; (d) R. Jana, S. Samanta and J. K. Ray, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2008, **49**, 851; (e) S. Samanta, H. Mohapatra, R. Jana and J. K. Ray, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2008, **49**, 7153.
- (a) S. Samanta, R. Jana and J. K. Ray, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2009, **50**, 6751; (b) S. Samanta, N. Yasmin, D. Kundu and J. K. Ray, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2010, **51**, 4132.
- S. Paul, T. Gorai, A. Kbley and J. K. Ray, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2011, **52**, 4051.
- C. Bäcktorp, L. Hagvall, A. Börje, A.-T. Karlberg, P.-O. Norrby and G. Nyman, *J. Chem. Theory Comput.*, 2008, **4**, 101.
- D. C. Braddock, I. D. MacGilp and B. G. Perry, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2000, **42**, 7527.

